

Unlocking Speech: Machine Learning for Intuitive Voice Recognition

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Abstract— Machine Learning is widely used to detect the movement of lips. It has been observed that the data generated through visual stir of mouth and corresponding audio are largely identified. This fact has been exploited for lip reading and for perfecting speech recognition. We propose a system that uses a CNN(Convolutional Neural Network) which is trained and used to descry the movement of lips and prognosticate the words being spoken. This trained CNN will be suitable to descry the words that are spoken within the videotape and display it in a textbook format. The CNN may also calculate on fresh information handed by the environment, knowledge of the language, and any residual hail. We hope to learn whether the application of machine literacy, more specifically the DNN(Deep Neural Network), could also be an applicable seeker for working the problem of lip reading. The main end of our design is to directly honour the expressions being spoken through automated lip reading.

Keywords— Visual Speech Recognition, Lip reading, OpenCV, neural network, CNN, DNN, 3D convolutions, object detection, data pre-processing, Python, Keras

I. INTRODUCTION

Visual lip-reading holds significance in human-computer interaction within noisy environments, especially for aiding individuals with hearing disabilities or assisting security forces in speech identification when audio records are unavailable. Similar to audio speech recognition, lip-reading systems encounter challenges due to variances in inputs such as facial features, skin colours, speaking speeds, and intensities, thus necessitating extensive research in the field of deep learning. The complexity of lip reading, wherein multiple words can appear indistinguishable when spoken, presents unique challenges that have spurred advancements in automated speech recognition using machine learning. The advent of Deep Learning and deep neural networks has notably enhanced the accuracy of automated lip-reading systems, facilitated by the extensive data sets available. The technique for automated lip reading involves four stages: face detection, cropping module, feature extraction, and text decoding, each playing a crucial role in interpreting lip movements.

The proposed system for automated lip reading implements a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) that undergoes several stages, beginning with face detection, followed by a cropping module, feature extraction, and text decoding. The system is tested using both 3 hidden layer architecture and 5 hidden layer architecture, with the former being prioritized due to computation constraints. The system architecture involves an input layer, three consecutive hidden layers with 32, 64, and 96 neurons, and an output layer, employing SoftMax subcaste for probability classification and max mum pooling to reduce parameters for subsequent layers. The system is trained with a variety of parameters, such as the number of epochs, the learning rate, and the optimizer, while the normalization of image frames is employed to ensure even training data, accounting for irregularities in speech patterns.

The system is designed to process video samples and convert them into subtitled videos through the application of a trained CNN. The delicacy of the system varies between 70 to 80 based on different video samples and exhibits improved performance with a 5X5X5 kernel. The envisioned applications for this system are diverse, including applications in fields such as forensics, film processing, and aiding individuals with hearing disabilities. The proposed model is anticipated to be further enhanced through the exploration of alternative content views and expansion to other language datasets and extended datasets, opening up avenues for broader application, such as CCTV usage.

Automated lip reading involves four key stages: face detection, cropping, feature extraction, and text decoding. Face detection algorithms aim to identify faces within an image. The cropping module isolates the region of interest, typically the lips. Feature extraction then extracts pertinent features. Finally, text decoding translates these features into meaningful text.

Fig. 1. Visualization of Lip Reading

II. RELATED WORK

Deciphering text from lip movements is a complex task, demanding comprehensive training of the model to accurately interpret lip movements.

Michael Wand and Jurgen Schmidhuber [3] developed a lipreading system capable of end-to-end training, requiring minimal frames of un-transcribed target data to significantly enhance recognition accuracy for the target speaker. They achieved speaker independence through domain-adversarial training integrated into the lipreader's architecture, which included a stack of feedforward and LSTM recurrent neural networks. Their primary objective was to reach an intermediate data representation that is agnostic to the data source, whether from the target or source speaker. They utilized TensorFlow's Momentum Optimizer with stochastic gradient descent to minimize multi-class cross-entropy and optimize the system.

Brendan Shillingford et al. [7] developed the most extensive visual speech recognition dataset to date, comprising pairs of text and video clips totaling 3,886 hours of video. Their integrated lip reading system included several components: a video processing pipeline that transformed raw video into stable lip videos and phoneme sequences, a scalable deep neural network that mapped lip videos to sequences of phoneme distributions, and a robust speech decoder for producing sequences of words.

Lele Chen and team took a different route, fusing audio and image embeddings to generate multiple lip images simultaneously. They introduced a novel correlation loss to synchronize lip and speech changes, making their model robust to various factors like lip shapes, view angles, and facial characteristics. Their approach, outlined in "Lip Reading at a Glance," leverages the observation that speech correlates with lip movements across different individuals. Now, onto Joon Son Chung and crew, who delved into sequence-to-sequence translator architectures for speech recognition. Their Watch, Listen, Attend, and Spell (WLAS) network transcribes mouth motion videos to characters. They implemented a curriculum learning strategy to speed up training and mitigate overfitting. Their dataset, "Lip Reading Sentences" (LRS), boasts over 100,000 natural sentences from British television. The unique aspect here is the model's ability to operate with dual attention mechanisms— over visual input only, audio input only, or both. With image and audio encoders and a character decoder, their model tackles the intricate task of lipreading, aiming to recognize phrases whether spoken with or without accompanying audio

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

We propose a system that will take in a video Fig. 2. Flow diagram input from the user. The video undergoes pre-processing, where it's segmented into individual frames to ensure uniformity and enhance face recognition. Subsequently, the focus shifts to detecting the region of interest, namely the mouth, which is then cropped out. This cropped region serves as input to a convolutional neural network (CNN) for subsequent processing. Within the CNN, visual features are extracted, facilitating model training, ultimately leading to the decoding of spoken words. Figure 2 illustrates the flow diagram of our proposed system.

A. Pre-processing

To begin with, the video is segmented into individual frames, typically captured in the RGB format. However, to streamline processing and reduce unnecessary parameter overhead, these RGB images are converted to grayscale. This conversion eliminates the extra parameters associated with RGB images, making the subsequent processing more efficient. The resulting grayscale frames are then forwarded for further processing [1][3].

B. Face Detection and Cropping

After obtaining frames from the video, our proposed system will initiate face detection within each frame, assuming a requirement for full frontal views only. We aim for simplicity, disregarding partial or side views. Utilizing the DLib face detector and landmark predictor with 68 landmarks, we leverage these features to identify faces within the frames. Frames lacking detected faces will be discarded from further processing [6].

The subsequent stage involves identifying our Region of Interest (ROI), specifically the lips and mouth region, utilizing the Haar cascade classifier. Once the mouth region is detected, cropping it out becomes necessary for lip movement detection and further system training. Additionally, standardizing the RGB channels to achieve zero mean and unit variance is crucial. Following this process, the images will be saved as a NumPy array, with the cropped mouth region images as values, resembling the representation depicted in Figure 4. The entire process of face detection and cropping is illustrated in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Face detection and cropping process

Fig. 4. Saved NumPy array sample

C. Feature extraction and normalization

Once the images are stored as an array, the next step involves extracting features from the Region of Interest (ROI). Spatio-temporal features are particularly important and are extracted from the ROI. These features are then fed into a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) as input for training the model [2].

Normalization of the image frames is imperative to ensure uniformity in the dataset. Variations in pronunciation duration among individuals can lead to inconsistencies during training and result interpretation. Therefore, normalization is employed to standardize the training data, addressing discrepancies arising from differences in pronunciation durations.

D. Text Classification and Decoding

Upon completion of normalization, the data is fed into the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for training and subsequent text decoding. The CNN autonomously learns through numerous epochs, exchanging learned information across multiple hidden layers. Decoding is achieved by aligning lip movements with the image data and cross-referencing them with the training dataset, facilitating prediction of the spoken word [4].

Following the prediction of words for each segment of the video, the next step involves aggregating these predicted words to reconstruct the original sentence spoken by the individual in the dataset. This aggregation process entails combining the predicted words in the correct order to form coherent sentences, mirroring the speech patterns and semantics of the original utterance.

E. Architecture

The proposed system architecture is structured around a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), comprising an input layer, three hidden layers, and an output layer. Within this framework, a SoftMax layer is employed as a probability classifier, while max pooling is utilized to reduce the parameter count for subsequent layers. The hidden layers consist of 32, 64, and 96 neurons across consecutive layers, respectively. While the system is evaluated using both 3-layer and 5-layer architectures, the 3-layer architecture is prioritized due to computational constraints associated with the 5-layer configuration. Figure 5 illustrates the representation of the CNN architecture.

Fig. 5. CNN Basic Architecture

IV. EXPERIMENT

A. Development Environment

The system has been deployed on a computing environment featuring an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 CPU clocked at 2.6 GHz, equipped with 8 GB of RAM, and supplemented by an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1650 graphics card boasting 4 GB of VRAM. The Operating system used is Windows 11. The implementation has been carried out using the Python 3.9 programming language.

The computer vision tasks, including image processing and classification, are facilitated by OpenCV. Additionally, we utilize Keras, Microsoft Cognitive Toolkit (CNTK), and Theano frameworks for various aspects of our system. Specifically, Keras is employed on top of TensorFlow for neural network implementation and training [10].

Unless stated otherwise, the model is trained using the following parameters:

- Number of epochs: 30, or training terminates if validation accuracy does not improve after 4 consecutive epochs.
- Learning rate - 1×10^{-4} .
- Optimizer- Adam15.

The predicted set of words is synchronized with the video sample and displayed as subtitles, as depicted in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Model Predicting the words spoken

B. Dataset

The GRID dataset comprises 34 subjects, each tasked with uttering 1000 phrases. These phrases typically follow a specific format, including a verb (4 options), color (4 options), preposition (4 options), alphabet (26 options), digit (0-9), and adverb (4 options). For example, a phrase might be 'put blue at A 1 now'. While the total vocabulary size is 51, the actual number of possibilities for each component of the phrase is constrained to the numbers specified in the brackets above. The videos are recorded in a controlled laboratory environment, as depicted in Figure 7 [11].

The evaluation process adheres to a rigorous quality protocol, beginning with the random division of data into train, validation, and test sets. The test set comprises 255 utterances for each speaker. Word error rates are calculated and reported as part of the evaluation. It's worth noting that some previous studies report word accuracies, which are defined as ($WAcc = 1 - WER$) [2], where WER stands for Word Error Rate. Fig.7.Still images from GRID dataset.

V. RESULTS

The proposed system has undergone training using the GRID CORPUS dataset, resulting in variable accuracy ranging between 70% to 80% on the chosen test dataset. Figure 8 illustrates the achieved accuracy while comparing different kernel sizes. As indicated in Table I, there's a noticeable increase in accuracy when the kernel size of the CNN is increased from 3X3X3 to 5X5X5, particularly with an increase in the number of epochs.

Fig. 8. Model Accuracy

TABLE I. KERNEL SIZE AND ACCURACY

Kernel Size	Dropout	Epochs	Accuracy
3X3X3	NO	14	75.84
5X5X5	NO	18	79.52

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

We've introduced Perception, a trained model leveraging AI techniques to translate silent video samples into subtitled videos. Utilizing a trained CNN, the accuracy ranges between 70% to 80% across various video samples, with notably higher accuracy observed when employing a 5X5X5 kernel.

This system has versatile applications across numerous fields, including forensics, film processing, assistance for the deaf and mute, and many others.

In the future, we could enhance this technique by exploring the detection of subject viewpoints beyond the frontal view, allowing its integration into CCTV environments. Furthermore, broadening the approach to include other language datasets and expanded datasets would enhance its versatility and applicability [5].

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